

Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract

Borrowed by psychology, reinforcement learning is the hottest algorithm presently. Indeed, reinforcement learning is not the only learning method in psychology. There are some other important mechanisms in psychology include innate behaviour and observational learning. They are especially important in the early stage and able to earn good rewards with less data. It's a good news to modelling. Instead, innate behaviour and observational learning are close to structural equation modelling. Unfortunately, this subject is not famous boost presently. In the speech, Icarus will explain the importance of observational learning, how to merge it with reinforcement learning with example and the future of observational learning.

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